

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1227 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
	In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:	

DEFINITION Yellowish colluvium above 1187 & 1173	Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 15% silt 65% sand 20%
Anthropoc <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles M <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Glass R	Geological <input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	Organic <input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth R <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
		Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit (1245)	
Eastern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1245 & 1187
Is covered by:	Covers: 1173 & 1188
Is cut by: 1170 & 1212	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
SV was despite the hot weather conditions very well observed.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: Central western edge of Trench B 2010.
Shape: long oval

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): No slope (ground slopes, but layer is constant)
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Z big pieces of roof tile together near NE corner of 1227, but no other clustering
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): increases a little as moves toward W because floor under slopes
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

please replace previous 1227

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Colluvial accumulation of soil south of the wall 1187. ^{and above 14} Soil covered the two slabs of the cistern (SU 1188) and the hifo floor (SU 1173).

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets): 2
 Sample quantity (buckets):
 Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):
 Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):
 Sample quantity (buckets):
 Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	Cynthia	on	26.07.2010
Revised by	AKM	on	26.07.2010
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